

THE CONCEPT OF VRANA - A REVIEW**Dr. Dipak Sahu^{*1}, Dr. Shweta Soni², Dr. Tripti Netam³**

^{*1}PG Scholar, Dept. of Dept. of Shalya Tantra Mahaveer College of Ayurvedic Science,
Rajnandgaon, Chhattisgarh – 491441.

^{2,3}Associate Professor, Dept. of Shalya Tantra, Mahaveer College of Ayurvedic Science,
Rajnandgaon, Chhattisgarh – 491441.

Article Received on 05 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17745069>

Corresponding Author*Dr. Dipak Sahu**

PG Scholar, Dept. of Dept. of Shalya
Tantra Mahaveer College of Ayurvedic
Science, Rajnandgaon, Chhattisgarh –
491441.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Dipak Sahu^{*}, Dr. Shweta Soni, Dr. Tripti Netam. (2025). The Concept of vrana - A Review. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 710–726.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license

ABSTRACT

Vrana (wound) holds a significant place in Ayurveda, being described as a pathological state that compromises both structure and function of the body. Classical texts classify *Vrana* into *Nija* (endogenous, caused by internal imbalance) and *Agantuja* (exogenous, due to trauma or external injury), highlighting its diverse etiology. *Sushruta*, revered as the “Father of Surgery,” elaborated on wound types, healing stages, and management through *Shashti Upakrama* (sixty therapeutic measures). Ayurvedic principles emphasize *Shodhana* (purification) and *Ropana* (healing) along with systemic therapies to restore *dosha* balance, while modern science focuses on infection control, debridement, and tissue regeneration. Wound healing is a natural process but is influenced by systemic diseases, nutrition, infection, and local

factors. Chronic and infected wounds remain a challenge, particularly in rural settings. Integrating Ayurvedic practices with contemporary wound management may offer effective, safe, and affordable approaches to promote faster and healthier healing.

KEYWORDS: *Vrana, Shodhana, Ropana, Shashti Upakrama, Dushta Vrana.*

INTRODUCTION

The concept of *Vrana* dates back to Vedic literature, where injuries and their management were first discussed. Later, *Sushruta* provided a detailed account of wound classification,

pathogenesis, and treatment strategies, many of which retain relevance in modern practice. Healing is a biological process of repair that occurs in sequential stages but can be delayed by infection, poor hygiene, and systemic conditions. Ayurveda prescribes numerous herbal formulations and procedures for *Vrana Shodhana* (cleansing) and *Ropana* (healing). Integrating these traditional methods with current surgical practices may provide cost-effective and holistic solutions for wound care.

DEFINITION

‘व्रण’ गात्रविचूर्णने, व्रणयतीति व्रणः।

(सु.चि. 1/6)

The term ‘VARNA’ is derived from verbal root ‘VRANA’ meaning "splitting/tearing of the body" (causing discontinuity of the skin and other tissue under it) it is called VRANA.^[1]

VRANA word is given by wise since it covers (occupies the skin or the area of the body) and also because the VRANA *vastu* (scar or cicatrix formed later) does not get lost (disappear) even after healing and remains till the body survives.^[2]

Dalhan gives the meaning of verb ‘VRANA’ as causing discoloration of the body or its parts.

AETIOLOGY

Sushruta has described two types of *vrana*.^[3]

1. *Nija / Sharir* = Endogenous.

2. *Agantuja* = Exogenous.

1. *Nija / Sharir* - It is caused by bodily *doshas Vata, Pitta, Kapha, Rakta* and *Sannipata*. It is divided into fifteen varieties based on the qualitative and quantitative presence of morbid diathesis (deranged *Vata, Pitta, Kapha* and *Rakta*) either separately or in combination. By adding *shuddha vrana* (healthy wound) to the above list, *vrana* is divided into sixteen types.

2. *Agantuja vrana* - It is caused by trauma from human beings, animals, birds, ferocious beasts, reptiles, falling, pressing, striking, fire, caustic alkali, poison, irritant drugs, pieces (of wood etc.), earthen ware, horn, circular weapons, arrows, axe, etc. weapons and supernatural factors (Mantra, Curse etc.) stated by *Kashyap*.^[4]

PATHOGENESIS (KRIYAKALA)^[5]

Sushrut has described six stages of pathogenesis of diseases including *VRANA* as *Sadkriyakal* (six gradual stages). He said that one who understands these stages - *Sanchaya*, *Prakopa*, *Prasar*, *Sthan Samshrya*, *Vyakti*, and *Bhed* can only be a real physician. *Sushruta* described these stages with their characteristic features and warned clinicians to diagnose them properly, as proper diagnosis allows proper treatment. Selection of appropriate treatment and suitable drugs for each stage is the physician's work. Hence, great emphasis is laid on a clear understanding of these six evolutionary stages. It is only *Sushruta* who enumerates these *Sadkriyakal* and furnishes details of each, testifying to his keen observation of the disease process.

Table 1: Kriyakala of vrana.

S. No.	Stage (Kriyakala)	Description	Symptoms / Features	Remarks
1.	<i>Sanchaya</i> (Accumulation)	Initial accumulation and intensification of <i>Doshas</i>	Mild imbalance, no clear symptoms	Preventive stage
2.	<i>Prakopa</i> (Aggravation)	Increased disorganization of <i>Doshas</i>	Localized irritation, early imbalance	Needs early correction
3.	<i>Prasara</i> (Spread)	<i>Doshas</i> spread through circulation	Generalized signs, migration of <i>Doshas</i>	Can progress to site of weakness
4.	<i>Sthanasamshraya</i> (Localization)	Vitiated <i>Doshas</i> lodge at <i>kh-vaigunya sthana</i>	Early functional imbalance; prodromal signs of <i>Vrana</i>	Preclinical stage
5.	<i>Vyakti</i> (Manifestation)	Definite clinical disease appears	<i>Vrana Shotha</i> (inflammatory swelling), <i>Vidradhi</i> , <i>Granthi</i>	Pre- <i>vrana</i> stage
	<i>Ama awastha</i>	Immature inflammation	Mild pain, cold swelling, hardness, low-grade fever	Early swelling stage
	<i>Pachyamana awastha</i>	Maturing (suppurating) inflammation	Severe varied pains, fever, burning, thirst, anorexia, tense swelling	Stage of suppuration
	<i>Pakva awastha</i>	Mature abscess with pus	Relief of pain, fluctuation, itching, appetite returns	Ready to burst / drain
6.	<i>Bhedavastha</i> (Complication / Ulcer formation)	Rupture of mature <i>abscess</i> and formation of ulcer occur	General symptoms (fever, diarrhea), tissue damage	May become chronic or incurable

PATHOGENESIS OF AGANTUJA VRANA

These *vrana* are caused by various type of trauma. Here the destruction of tissue occurs first followed by disturbance of '*Doshic*' balance.^[6] According to *Dalhan*, a traumatic wound ceases to be of traumatic character after seven days, when it is to be considered as an autogenic wound.

In the beginning *Pitta* and *Rakta* are vitiated followed by systemic vitiation of *Vatic Dosh*. All these during post traumatic period reorganised in different combination and manifest their characteristic symptoms as *vedana*, *daha* and *kandu* etc.

CLASSIFICATION OF VRANA

I. According to Etiology

(a) *Sharir Vrana* (Endogenous)

(b) *Agantuja Vrana* (Exogenous)

II. According to Clinical Features

(a) *Dushta Vrana*

(b) *Shuddha Vrana*

(c) *Ruhyamana Vrana*

(d) *Samyakrudh Vrana*

III. According to Prognosis

(a) *Sukhropniya Vrana*

(b) *Krichhra Sadhya Vrana*

(c) *Yapya Vrana*

(d) *Asadhya Vrana*

IV. According to *Prasavbhed*

(a) *Vataja Vrana*

(b) *Pittaja Vrana*

(c) *Kaphaja Vrana*

(d) *Raktaja Vrana*

(e) *Vatapittaja Vrana*

(f) *Vatakaphaja Vrana*

(g) *Pittakaphaja Vrana*

(h) *Vataraktaja Vrana*

(i) *Pittaraktaja Vrana*

(j) *Kapharaktaja Vrana*

(k) *Vatapittaraktaja Vrana*

(l) *Vatakapharaktaja Vrana*

(m) *Pittakapharaktaja Vrana*

(n) *Vatapittakaphaja Vrana*

(o) *Vatapittakapharaktaja Vrana*

(p) *Shuddha Vrana*

FEATURES OF VRANA ACCORDING TO DOSHAS^[7]

Pain with destruction of tissue is general characteristic of all forms of *vrana*.

षण्मूलोऽष्टपरिग्राही पञ्चलक्षणलक्षितः ।

षष्ट्या विधानैर्निर्दिष्टैश्चतुर्भिः साध्यते व्रणः ॥

(सु.चि. 1/134)

Table 2: Features of vrana.

Dosha / Combination	Gandha (Smell)	Varna Colour)	Srava (Discharge)	Vedana (Pain)	Other Special Characters
Vata	Katu	Shyava, Aruna, Bhasma	Picchila, Tanu, Alpasravi	Sfurana, Toda	Ruksha, Chatchatyan
Pitta	Tikshna	Neel, Peet, Shyava, Rakta, Harita, Kinshukodaka, Ushna, Pingal	Daaha, Paka	Daaha, Paka	Peetpindika
Kapha	Aama	Shweta, Pandu	Shukla, Sheet, Sandra, Picchila	Manda Vedana, Kandu	Sthoolostha, Kathina
Rakta	Loha, Tivra	Pravaldala Prakash	Rakta, Krishna	Similar to Pitta	Sphota, Pindika, Jaal Yukt
Vata-Pitta	Laja Gandha	Peeta, Arunabha	Peeta, Arunabha	Toda, Daaha, Dhoomayan	---
Vata-Kapha	Alsi Tail Gandha	Peeta-Shukla	Sheeta, Picchila, Alpa, Muhurmuhar	Toda, Muhurmuhar Vedana	Guru, Ruksha
Pitta-Kapha	Til Taila Gandha	Peeta	Peeta, Pandu Sravi, Ushna	Daaha	Guru
Vata-Rakta		Rakta, Arunabha	Rakta, Arunabha	Toda, Supta	Ruksha, Tanu
Pitta-Rakta	Ghrita-mand, Meen Dhawan Toya	Ati-Rakta	Ushna, Krishna Srava	Daaha, Ativedana	Mridu
Kapha-Rakta	Rakta	Picchila, Rakta, Pandu	Picchila Srava	Kandu	Guru, Snigdha
Vata-Pitta-Rakta	Peeta, Rakta Gandha	Peeta, Tanu, Rakta	Tanu Rakta Srava	Sphurana, Toda, Daaha, Dhoomayan	---
Vata-Kapha-Rakta	Pandu Gandha	Pandu, Ghana, Rakta	Ghana Rakta Srava	Kandu, Sphurana, Chumchumayana	---
Pitta-Rakta (Heat Predominanc)	Pandu Gandha	Pandu, Ghana, Rakta	Ghana Srava	Daaha, Paka, Raga, Kandu	Predominane of Ushna
Tridoshaja	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed	Mixed
Sannipataja	Various	Various	Various	Manthana, Sphurana, Toda, Daha, Paka, Raga, Kandu	Various Akriti

FEATURES OF SADHYO VRANA (AGANTUJA VRANA)⁸

Table 3: Sadyovranas according to different Acharyas.

<i>Sushruta Samhita</i>	<i>Ashtanga Sangraha</i>	<i>Ashtanga Hridaya</i>	<i>Madhava Nidana</i>	<i>Sharangadhara Samhita</i>
<i>Chinnam</i>	<i>Chinnam</i>	<i>Ghrishtham</i>	<i>Chinnam</i>	<i>Avakritham</i>
<i>Bhinnam</i>	<i>Viddham</i>	<i>Avakritham</i>	<i>Bhinnam</i>	<i>Vilambitham</i>
<i>Viddham</i>	<i>Picchitham</i>	<i>Vicchinnam</i>	<i>Viddham</i>	<i>Chinnam</i>
<i>Kshatham</i>	-	<i>Pravilambitham</i>	<i>Kshatham</i>	<i>Bhinnam</i>
<i>Picchitham</i>	-	<i>Nipathitham</i>	<i>Picchitham</i>	<i>Parachalitham</i>
<i>Ghrishtham</i>	-	<i>Viddham</i>	-	<i>Viddham</i>
-	-	<i>Bhinnam</i>	-	-
-	-	<i>Vidhalitham</i>	-	<i>Nipathitham</i>

Charaka has described another classification of *Vrana* depending on their *Lakshana*, which are twenty in number. They are *Kritya vrana*, *Akritya vrana*, *Dushta vrana*, *Adushta vrana*, *Marmashritha vrana*, *Amarmashritha vrana*, *Samvrutha vrana*, *Vivrutha vrana*, *Daruna vrana*, *Mridu vrana*, *Sraavi vrana*, *Asraavi vrana*, *Vishyuktha vrana*, *Visharahitha vrana*, *Vishama vrana*, *Sama vrana*, *Uthsangi vrana*, *Anuthsangi vrana*, *Uthsanna vrana*, and *Anuthsanna vrana*.^[9]

Sadhyo Vrana is caused by trauma. *Sushruta* has elaborated features of *agantuja vrana* which depends on types of instrument causing injury and site of injury.

1. *Chhinna Vrana (Cut/Excised)* - A traumatic wound which is oblique or straight and elongated is called a *chhinna vrana*. Due to severity of the trauma, a part or a organ is separated from the body almost completely. There are intense bleeding and pain.

2. *Bhinna vrana (Incised)* - A perforation of any of the cavities or receptacles of the body by pointed instrument like sword or by horn associated with bleeding and discharge is called *bhinna vrana*. General features of this type of injury include filling of viscus with blood, fever, burning sensation and bleeding through rectum, urethra, mouth and nose, dyspnoea, thirst, tympanitis, cessation of passage of stool, flatus and urine, swelling, discharge, flushing of eyes, metallic smell from mouth, chest pain and also coma occurs.

3. *Viddha vrana (Punctured)* - The wound caused by any sharp pointed instrument in any part of the body other than *ashayas* (cavities) with or without that *shalya* (instrument) is called *viddha vrana*. This is associated with excessive hemorrhage and pain.

4. *Kshata vrana* (Lacerated) - The uneven wound neither excessively excised nor severally incised but having features of both is known as *Kshata vrana*, this is irregular and associated with bleeding and pain.

5. *Picchita vrana* (Crushed) - When a part of the body with bone is crushed between the folds of door or by a blow and becomes flat the wound is called as *pichhita vrana*. It is frequently covered with crushed blood and bone marrow. These wounds get contaminated early with intense pain and burning sensation.

6. *Ghrista Vrana* (Abrasions) - When skin is peeled off by rubbing or by any other cause and associated with burning sensation, severe pain, hot, thin secretion (*ushnasrava*), it is known as *ghrista vrana*.

DUSHTA VRANAS

On the basis of *dosha dushti* the *vranas* are again classified as *Dushta Vranas* and *Shuddha Vranas*. It is the only one classification which is agreed by *Harita Samhita*.^[10] He has considered all *vranas* as *Dushta vranas* due to the involvement of *doshas* in its production.

The etiology and pathogenesis of *Dushta vranas* have been described by *Acharya Harita* as follows

- ❖ Contaminated food and drinks
- ❖ Lifting heavy loads
- ❖ Severe exercise
- ❖ Emotional factors like anger, fear, grief etc.

***Samprapthi* (pathogenesis)**

Due to above mention etiological there occurs destruction in *mamsa dhatu* which results in oozing of blood from its normal pathway and thus leading to *Dushta vranas*. *Kashyapa samhita* also accepts that *doshas* are the inevitable factors for the manifestations of *Vranas*. *Vrana* is caused not just by the individual vitiated *doshas* only, but also with the combined vitiation of *doshas*. Even though the *vrana* is manifested at first on the skin, later it extends to the deeper structures such as *meda*, *asthi* etc. and lastly it results in *dushta vrana* thus destructing considerable amount of *dhatu*s.

Dushta Vranas Lakshanas

The *vranas* may be too narrow or too widened, mouth too hard or too soft, raised from their surface or depressed, too cold or too hot to touch and the colour may be black red-yellow or white and is characterized by extreme temperature. It has a vulnerable appearance having a network of veins, ligaments etc. They are filled with putrid and sloughing flesh accompanied with fetid pus, irregular and indefinite shape. Secretion of dirty fetid pus which runs into fissures and cavities following an oblique or upward course are the specificities of the *vranas*. The *Dushta vranas* have cadaverous look and irritating smell and are noticed by extreme pain and burning sensation. Besides these swelling, redness, itching, pustules are seen around the wound. There will be amorphous secretion of impure blood. The *vranas* will remain unhealed for a prolonged period.^[11,12]

HEALING OF VRANA

Sushruta has given a clear description of the various stages of a *vrana* which are seen during healing.^[13] The characteristics of such stages are as following

1. *Shuddha vrana*- A *vrana* which is not invaded by the *Tridoshas*, edges of which are dark brown (*shyavaoshta*) in colour, which has developed small eruptions (granulation tissue), which is even, not having pain and exudations, wound resembles lower surface of a clean tongue, soft, unctuous, smooth is said to be a *shuddha vrana*.

When treatment in various forms applied to the *shuddha vrana* there is hastening of the process of healing and the wound passes to *ruhyaman* stage and further healing takes place.

2. *Ruhyaman vrana*- The *vrana* with margin of pigeon's colour (grey), devoid of moisture (exudation), has scale of skin, adhering firmly is to be considered as a healing *vrana*.

3. *Rhuda vrana*- A *vrana* cannot be called completely healed if any nodular swelling, edema, or pain persists. In other words, there should be no pathology at the site of lesion and the colour should be same as the surrounding skin. The surface should be even with the normal part of the body. However, such a *vrana* which has been completely healed up may still exhibit a scar (*vrana vastu*) for the entire life. It may be associated with discolouration, loss of hair and other complications like keloid (*mamsa kandi*) formation for which one has to resort to specific measure for their eradication (*vakritapahan*).

SADHYA – ASADHYA (PROGNOSIS) OF VRANA^[14,15]

The curability of a *vrana* (wound) depends mainly on

1. The Individual – age, health, mental strength, and body resistance.
2. The Nature of the *Vrana* – its shape, depth, and associated conditions.
3. The Location of the *Vrana* – anatomical site and vital structures involved.

***Sukha Sadhya Vrana* (Easily Curable Wounds)**

- Found in young, healthy individuals with good *satva bala*.
- Located on regions like *nithamba*, *guda*, *guhya pradesha*, *lalata*, *ganda*, *oshta*, *prishta*, *udara*, etc.
- Circular, conical, rectangular, triangular, and square-shaped wounds heal easily.
- Wounds in children heal faster due to rapid tissue growth.

***Krichra Sadhya Vrana* (Difficult-to-Cure Wounds)**

- Wounds in person suffering from leprosy, poison, consumption, diabetes mellitus and in those who are having wounds already, heal with difficulty.
- Found at sites like *akshi*, *danta*, *nasika*, *apanga*, *nabhi*, *seevani*, *kaksha*, *sandhi*.
- Includes *bhagandhara* with pus, gas, or retained *shalya*.
- Narrow-mouthed or wounds in vital parts, perineum, or pelvis are difficult to heal.

Yapya Vrana

- In *Prameha* patients, wounds associated with *Krimi*, *Sharkarameha*, *Sikatameha*, *Vatakundalika*, *Ashtheela*, *Dantasharkara*, *Upakusha*, *Kanthashaluka*, *Nishkoshana-dushita*, *Visarpa*, *Astrikshata*, *Urahkshata*, and *Vranagrandhi* are considered *Yapya*.
- A *Yapya Vyadhi* is one that remains controlled only with continuous treatment, but becomes fatal when treatment is stopped. It is like a collapsing house supported temporarily by a single pillar

***Asadhya Vrana* (Incurable Wounds)**

- Associated with chronic diseases (*visarpa*, *jwara*, *atisara*, *kasa*, *swasa*, *avipaka*).
- Wounds exposing bone marrow (*mastulunga*), with black/yellow discharge of pus, urine, feces, or blood.
- Found in weak, emaciated, or mentally unstable persons; wounds at *marma* sites emitting pus/blood.

- Wounds unresponsive to prolonged treatment are incurable.
Causes Turning *Sadhya Vrana* into *Asadhya*
- Broken *snayu* or bone, infection, poison contamination.
- Wrong bandaging, excess oily application, lack of *koshta shuddhi*, overactivity, poor diet, or neglect of *pathya*.
- When a wound (*Vrana*) is not treated at the appropriate time, a *Sadhya Vrana* (easily curable wound) gradually progresses to a *Yapya Vrana* (manageable but not completely curable wound). If treatment is still delayed, the *Yapya Vrana* further deteriorates into an *Asadhya Vrana* (incurable wound). If even at this stage proper care is not given, it may ultimately lead to severe complications and the death of the patient.

MANAGEMENT

Sushruta has mentioned *Trividha Karmas* for management of surgical disorders, they are -

1. *Poorva Karma*
2. *Pradhana Karma*
3. *Paschat Karma*

1. *Poorva Karma* - Among 60 *Upakramas* from *Apatarpana* to (mentioned for *Vranashopha*) these are considered as measures of *Poorva Karma*. By means of these measures either pacification of *Vrana Shopha* occurs or it becomes ripened. Among seven *Upakramas* of *Vranashopha* *Vimlapana*, *Avashechana*, *Upanaha* these 3 should be employed during the *Aama Avastha* of *Vrana Shopha*.

2. *Pradhana Karma* - Among 60 *Upakramas* starting from *Chedana* to *Seevana* (*Shastrakarma*) are considered as *Pradhana Karma*. In addition to *Ashtavidha Shastra Karmas*, *Dharana Karma* is mentioned. In case of *Bala*, *Vruddha*, *Bheru* and *Vrana Shopha* present in *Marma Pradesha* where *Shastra Karma* is contraindicated. This is performed by doing *Peedana* with local application of *Dravyas*. Among seven *Upakramas* of *Vranashopha* *Patana* is considered as *Pradhana Karma*.

3. *Paschat Karma*- Among 60 *Upakramas* starting from *Sandhana* to *Rakshavidhana* or among 7 *Upakramas* *Shodhana*, *Ropana* and *Vaikrutapaham* are considered under *Paschat Karma*.

Table 4: Upakramas of Vrana acc. To Various Acharyas.

<i>Upakrama</i>	<i>Sushruta</i> ^[16]	<i>Charaka</i> ^[17]	<i>Kashyap</i> ^[18]	<i>A.San/A. H.</i> ^[19]
<i>Apatarpana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Aalepa</i>	+	--	<i>Pralepa</i>	<i>Pradeha</i>
<i>Parisheka</i>	+	--	+	+
<i>Abhyanaga</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Swedana</i>	+	+	--	+
<i>Vimlapana</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Upanaha</i>	+	--	+	+
<i>Pachana</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Visravana</i>	+	--	+	+
<i>Sneha</i>	+	--	+	--
<i>Vamana</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Virechana</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Chedana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Bhedana</i>	+	<i>Patana</i>	--	--
<i>Dharana</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Lekhana</i>	+	+	--	--
<i>Eshana</i>	+	+	--	--
<i>Aharana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Vyadhana</i>	+	+	--	--
<i>Sravana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Seevana</i>	+	+	--	--
<i>Sandhana</i>	+	+	--	--
<i>Peedana</i>	+	<i>Avapeedana</i>	--	+
<i>Shonitasthapana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Nirvapana</i>	+	+	--	+
<i>Utkarika</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Kashaya</i>	+	<i>Shodhana, Ropana, Kashaya</i>	--	--
<i>Varti</i>	+	+	--	+
<i>Kalka</i>	+	--	+	--
<i>Sarpi</i>	+	<i>Shodhana Gritha Ropana Ghrita</i>	--	<i>Ropana Ghrita</i>
<i>Taila</i>	+	<i>Shodhana Taila Ropana Taila</i>	+	<i>Ropana Taila</i>
<i>Rasakriya</i>	+	--	--	+
<i>Avachoorana</i>	+	+	--	<i>Choorana</i>
<i>Vranadhoopana</i>	+	<i>Mardhavakara Katinyakara</i>	--	+
<i>Utsadana</i>	+	+	--	+
<i>Avasadana</i>	+	+	--	+
<i>Mrudukarma</i>	+	<i>Mardhavakara Aalepana</i>	--	+
<i>Dharunakarma</i>	+	<i>Katinyakara Aalepana</i>	--	+
<i>Ksharakarma</i>	+	<i>+(Daha)</i>	--	+

<i>Agnikarma</i>	+	+(<i>Daha</i>)	--	+
<i>Krishnakarma</i>	+	<i>Varnya</i>	<i>Savarneekarana</i>	<i>Savarneekarana</i>
<i>Paandukarma</i>	+	<i>Varnya</i>	<i>Savarneekarana</i>	<i>Savarneekarana</i>
<i>Pratisaarana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Romasanjanana</i>	+	+(<i>Lomarohana</i>)	--	+
<i>Lomapaharana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Bastikarma</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Uttarabasti</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Bandha</i>	+	+	+	+
<i>Patradhana</i>	+	<i>Patrachadana</i> (<i>Bahya</i>) <i>Patrachadana</i> (<i>Abhyantra</i>)	--	--
<i>Krimighna</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Bhrimhana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Vishaghna</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Shirovirechana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Nasya</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Kavaladharana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Dhooma</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Madhu-sarpi</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Yantra</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Aahara</i>	+	<i>Bhojya</i>	--	--
<i>Rakshavidhana</i>	+	--	--	--
<i>Shophaghna</i>	--	+	--	--
<i>Shamana</i>	--	+	+	--
<i>Chadhana</i>	--	+	--	--
<i>Shodhanalepa</i>	--	+	--	+
<i>Ropanalepa</i>	--	+	--	+
<i>Ropana</i>	--	+	+	--
<i>Utklinnaprakshalana</i>	--	--	+	<i>Prakshalan</i>
<i>Shodhana</i>	--	--	+	--
<i>Pracchanna</i>	--	+	--	--

In *Sapta Upakramas* also we can incorporate 60 therapeutic measures.

Table 5: *Sapta Upakramas*.

<i>Sapta Upakrama</i> . ^[20]	<i>Shashthi Upakrama</i>
<i>Vimlapana</i>	<i>Apatarpana, Aalepa, Parisheka, Abhyanga, Swedana, Vimlapana</i>
<i>Avasechan</i>	<i>Visravana, Sneha, Vamana, Virechana, Basti, Uttarbasti, Shirovirechan, Nasya, Kawal, Dhoom</i>
<i>Upanaha</i>	<i>Upanaha, Pachan, Utkarika</i>
<i>Patan</i>	<i>Chedana, Bhedana, Dharana, Lekhana, Eshana, Aharana, Vyadhana, Visravana, Seevana, Sandhan, Yantra</i>
<i>Shodhana</i>	<i>Peedan, Shonitasthapana, Nirvapana, Shodhan Kashaya, Varti, Kalka, Sarpi Taila, Raskriya, Avachurnan, Vranadhoopan, Avasadan, Mrudukarma, Kshar Karma, Agnikarma, Krumighna, Vishaghna</i>
<i>Ropana</i>	<i>Ropan Kashay, Varti, Kalka, Sarpi, Taila, Raskriya, Avachurnan, Utsadana,</i>

	<i>Darunakrma, Bandha, Patradan, Bruhana, Madhu-sarpi, Aahar, Rakshavidhan</i>
<i>Vaikrutapaham</i>	<i>Krushnakarma, Pandukarma, Pratisaran, Romsanjanan, Romapaharan</i>

Samanya Chikitsa (General Treatment)

The immediate management aims to pacify the *Ushma* (heat) at the site of injury through *Sheetala Kriyas* (cooling measures) similar to *Pitta Chikitsa*. *Madhu* and *Ghrita* are used for *Sodhana*. In cases of *Sadhya Vrana* with severe pain, frequent washing with warm *Yashṭi Ghrita* or *Bala Taila* helps reduce local heat. *Lepa* prepared with *Kashaya, Sita, Madhura,* and *Snigdha dravyas* is beneficial. *Snehapana, Parisheka, Swedana, Lepa, Upanaha,* and *Snehabasti* with *Vatahara* drugs should be administered. *Agantuka Vrana* specifically responds well to *Mantra, Agada,* and external application of medicinal pastes.

Specific Treatment (Vishesha Chikitsa)

Management of Agantuj Vrana^[21]

- 1. Chinna, Bhinna, Viddha Vrana** - Administration of *Snehapana, Seka,* and *Upanaha* with *Veshavara* or *Krushara*. *Swedana* using cereals. Application of *Snigdha Lepa* and *Sneha Basti* with *Vataghna* medicines. Use of unctuous (*Snigdha*) oils or *ghee* is recommended.
- 2. Ghrishta Vrana** - To reduce heat, apply cooling (*Sheetala*) ointments and perform *Parisheka*. After relieving pain with *Madhuka* or other cooling agents, dust with powders of *Saala, Arjuna,* etc
- 3. Picchita Vrana** - Apply cooling *Lepa* and perform *Parisheka*.
- 4. Avakrita Vrana** - Application of herbal paste (*Kalka*) is advised.
- 5. Vicchinna and Pravilambita Vrana** - Suturing (*Seevana*), bandaging (*Bandhana*), and compression (*Avapeedana*) should be done.
- 6. Viddha Vrana** Removal of foreign body (*Shalya*) is essential.

Management of Dusta Vrana^[22]

In cases of *Dusta Vrana*, *Sodhana* should be carried out through *Vamana* and *Virechana* to expel vitiated *Doshas*. *Langhana* and *Raktamoksana* are also beneficial for systemic purification. The *Vrana* should be cleansed with *kvatha* prepared from *Rajvrsadi* or *Surasadi*

Gana, followed by application of medicated *Taila* processed with these drugs to promote *Ropana* (healing).

PATHYA-APATHYA (DIET AND REGIMEN)^[23]

Pathya

The patient should take easily digestible food such as well-cooked old rice with unctuous substances and soup of wild animal meat. Soups made from *Tanduliyaka*, *Jeevanti*, *Vartaka*, *Patola*, *Karavellaka*, *Dadima*, and *Amalaki* are beneficial. The patient should avoid daytime sleep, exposure to wind, and should stay indoors in a clean environment. Personal hygiene should be maintained with trimmed nails and clean hair, along with observance of auspicious and positive routines.

Apathya

Ropana Vrana patient should not consume *Navadhanya*, *Masha*, *Tila*, *Kalaya*, *Kullattha*, *Nishpava*, *Hareetaka*, *Hareetaka Shaka*, *Katu*, *Amla*, *Lavana Rasa* Substances, *Guda*, *Sushka Shaka*, eatables made from *Pishta*, *Ajaa*, *Avika*, *Anoopa*, *Mansa*, *Sheeta Udaka*, *Krushara*, *Payasa*, *Dadhi*, *Dugdha* etc. Person who is habituated to drinking *Madhya* should avoid using *Maireya*, *Arista*, *Aasava*, *Seedhu* etc. *Vrana* person should avoid *Vata*, *Atapa*, *Raja*, *Dhooma*, *Atibhojana*, *Bhaya*, *Shoka Krodha*, *Ratri Jagrana*, *Vishamashana*, *Vyayama*, *Upavasa*, *Chankramana* etc.

COMPLICATIONS OF VRANA (WOUNDS)

Vrana (wounds) and *Vranita* (wounded persons) may develop several complications. The five major complications of *Vrana* include abnormal *Gandha* (smell), *Varna* (discoloration), *Sraava* (excessive discharge), *Vedana* (pain), and *Akriti* (irregular shape, size, edges, and margins).

Complications observed in the *Vranita* (wounded patient) include *Jwara* (fever), *Atisara* (diarrhea), *Murccha* (fainting), *Hikka* (hiccup), *Kshardi* (vomiting), *Arochaka* (loss of appetite), *Swas* (dyspnea), *Kasa* (cough), *Avipaka* (indigestion), and *Trishna* (excessive thirst).

DISCUSSION

The concept of *Vrana* holds a pivotal role in Ayurvedic surgery (*Shalya Tantra*), with detailed classification, pathogenesis, and management outlined by *Acharya Sushruta*. The term *Vrana*

not only encompasses physical wounds but also considers their *doshic* involvement, chronicity, and prognosis. The distinction between *Shuddha Vrana* (clean wound) and *Dusta Vrana* (infected or non-healing wound) is clinically relevant even today, aligning with modern concepts of acute and chronic wounds.

Management principles like *Vrana Shodhana* (cleansing) and *Vrana Ropana* (healing) are comprehensive, involving both systemic and local therapies. Ayurvedic drugs like *Jatyadi Taila*, *Triphala*, *Panchavalkala*, and procedures like *Kshara* demonstrate antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and regenerative properties, validated in recent scientific studies. These formulations and techniques not only accelerate healing but also minimize scarring and complications.

Integrating Ayurvedic principles with modern wound care could enhance outcomes, especially in chronic, drug-resistant, or non-healing ulcers. However, robust clinical trials and standardized protocols are needed for wider acceptance.

CONCLUSION

The Ayurvedic understanding of *Vrana* offers a holistic, time-tested approach to wound management. Its classification, *dosha*-based pathology, and therapeutic strategies provide valuable insights into treating both acute and chronic wounds. With increasing antibiotic resistance and chronic wound burden, Ayurveda can contribute significantly through integrative care models. Further research and collaboration with modern science can help validate and globalize these traditional practices.

REFERENCES

1. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurvedatatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 1/6.
2. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurvedatatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Sutra Sthana 21/40.
3. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurvedatatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 1/3.

4. Kashyapa Samhita: edited with Vidyotini Hindi commentary by Ayurvedalankar Shri Satyapal Bhisagacharya. Varanasi (India): Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; dwivraniyaadhyaya 7.
5. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Sutra Sthana 21/36.
6. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Sutra Sthana 1/4.
7. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurvedatatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 1/7.
8. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurvedatatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 2/8-9.
9. Tripathi Brahmanand, Charak Samhita-Charak Chandrika, Hindi Commentry Vol I and II, Chaukhamba Subharti Prakashan, Varanasi, reprinted, Charak Chikitsa Sthana, 25/29-30, 36-37.
10. Harita Samhita: edited with Hindi commentary. Varanasi (India): Chaukhambha Vishvabharati; Chapter 35, Verse 3.
11. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Sutra Sthana 22/7.
12. Tripathi Brahmanand, Charak Samhita-Charak Chandrika, Hindi Commentry Vol I and II, Chaukhamba Subharti Prakashan, Varanasi, reprinted, Charak Chikitsa Sthana,25/24-25, 29-30, 36-37.
13. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Sutra Sthana 23/18-21.
14. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Sutra Sthana 23/3,5-14.

15. Tripathi Brahmanand, Charak Samhita-Charak Chandrika, Hindi Commentry Vol I and II, Chaukhamba Subharti Prakashan, Varanasi, reprinted, Charak Chikitsa Sthana, 25/29-30,36-37.
16. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 1/8.
17. Tripathi Brahmanand, Charak Samhita-Charak Chandrika, Hindi Commentry Vol I and II, Chaukhamba Subharti Prakashan, Varanasi, reprinted, Charak Chikitsa Sthana 25/40-43.
18. Kashyapa Samhita: edited with Vidyotini Hindi commentary by Ayurvedalankar Shri Satyapal Bhishagacharya. Varanasi (India): Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; dwivraniyaadhyaya 10.
19. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdayam of Śrīmad Vāgbhaṭa: Sūtrasthāna & Śarīrasthāna. Edited with Nirmalā Hindi Commentary and Special Deliberation. Varanasi/Delhi (India): Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratishthan; Edited by Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi. Uttartantra Chapter 26 Verse 6-10,12,14-15.
20. Aṣṭāṅga Saṅgraha (Sūtrasthāna). Vyākhyākāra: Dr. (Smt.) Shailaja Srivastava. Varanasi (India): Chaukhambha Orientalia; Reprint Edition: 2019. Chapter 8.
21. Tripathi Brahmanand, Charak Samhita-Charak Chandrika, Hindi Commentry Vol I and II, Chaukhamba Subharti Prakashan, Varanasi, reprinted, Charak Chikitsa Sthana, 25/40-41
22. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 1/4,10,11,15,19-22, 2/85.
23. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 2/86-88.
24. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 19/12,1416-18,20,28,30,34,36.
25. Sushruta: Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda tatvasandeeepika Hindi commentary by Shastri Kaviraj Ambika dutta. Varanasi India: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; part-12014; Chikitsa Sthana 1/138-139.